

Climate change and migration in Sahel region: The bane of food security in Nigeria

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Abstract

Climate changes of deforestation, desertification, degradation, among others in Sahel region has widely resulted in irregular migration of cattle herders across borders to Nigeria for greener pastures with attendant consequences or threats to food supply thereby exacerbating poverty in Nigeria. The threat to food security emanates from the decline of the environmental conditions affecting agriculture, resulting in resource scarcity often leads to violent conflict, cost increase in food prices to outright food shortages. Climate change has been observed to accelerate the displacement of people when communities are overwhelmed by flood, water dried up for crops cultivation, alarming levels of deforestation, soil degradation, water and air pollution or when there are upheavals and violent conflicts between forced cattle migrants and farmers, claiming ownership of farm lands resulting in shortage in food supplies, income earning and poverty in Nigeria and Africa in general. The paper examines the effects of climate change on farming activities in Sahel region and the impact of migrated pastoralists' struggle with the aboriginal farmers over crop lands in various parts of the country on food security in Nigeria. The paper uses frustration-aggression theory as its theoretical framework. Qualitative data was utilized, sourced from textbooks, journals, the internet, among others. From the findings, it was concluded that human activities and natural occurrences have rendered Sahel environment hostile to farming particularly the pastoralists who migrate to Nigeria for better option. That their migration to Nigeria has accentuated resource conflict with the traditional farmers leading to the progressive effects on food production, food security and poverty. It was recommended that the inhabitants of Sahel environment should take to biofuel as alternative to fossil fuels to reduce climate change, the Nigeria Immigration Service should effectively guard the border movement of illegal aliens to forestall food insecurity in order to lift people above poverty in Nigeria, among others.

Keywords: Climate change, Food, Migration, Sahel region, Security.

INTRODUCTION

Based on the nine countries of the CILSS (Permanent Inter-States Committee for Drought Control in the Sahel), the countries covering the Sahel region are: Chad, Niger, Mauritania, Senegal, Gambia, Guinea-Bissau, Mali, Cape Verde, and Burkina Faso, with a population close to 60 million and a total area of 5.4 million km². There are other countries, serving as its extension such as the north of Ethiopia or Sudan. The Sahel is between the arid north and the green tropical forest in the south and borders the maritime coast in the west. Its vegetation is primarily made up of savanna-typical bushes, trees and grasses with increasing density from north to south, representing the change from semi-arid grasslands to thorny savanna (Van Keulen, Verhagen, Tekken & Battaglini, 2011). In all Sahel countries, annual rainfall quantity and distribution vary greatly, with scarcity of portable water. Apart from erratic rainfall patterns, unfavorable socio-economic conditions and poor soils are key agricultural development problems (Breman, 1990). In dry years, the livelihood of rural population is threatened, thereby contributing to a vicious circle of underdevelopment, resource depletion and poverty (Lüdeke, Petschel-Held & Schellnhuber, 2004). Changes in rainfall patterns, temperatures and severity of extreme events have direct impacts on crop yields with possibly severe consequences for the food security situation. The countries in Sahel regions, include Chad, Cameroon, Niger and Nigeria neighbouring the Central African Republic and Libya, have politically coordinated to address the decline of the Lake Chad through the Lake Chad Basin Commission and also to manage the surrounding lands, but every effort has been undermined by climate change, exacerbated by deforestation and desertification. In addition, deforestation exacerbates desertification since the removal of sun-blocking cover dries up the land and roots of trees serve to bind the soil difficult for crops to growth for better yields and livestock to graze (Hough, Malik, Moran, & Pilbeam, 2015)

LITERATURE REVIEW

Climate change and migration in Nigeria

The continued environment degradation of parts of Northern Nigeria which has resulted in the loss of grazing fields has induced a southward movement of pastoralists and the major consequences of this migration pattern is the incessant violent clashes between farmer in the host communities and herders. The pattern of conflict has led to disruption of agricultural activities, huge losses in human lives and destruction of farm settlements and communities. The pattern of conflict has increased armed trafficking across the countries. Some herders have resorted to using their acquired armed in perpetrating crimes such as kidnapping, armed robbery and rape, hence worsening the security situation in the country. Climate change has made farming so difficult in the Sahel because of scanty and unreliable rainfall and poor soils. So for centuries, many people have raised livestock instead, moving their herds periodically to find fresh pastures and allow the land to recover (Davis, 2022). Pastoral nomads are herders who wander endlessly in search of water and grazing land for their animals. Once their herds have grazed an area, the nomads move on by given marginal grazing land a chance to recover. The Sahelian countries (CILSS), are among the poorest countries in the world with the most degraded environments. They are also among the countries that are the most vulnerable to the estimated effects of climate change. The persistent drought in the Sudan and Sahel savannah areas has forced many pastoralists out of the region towards the guinea savannah and rain forest areas. This has resulted to increased pressure on lands in these areas. Fallow grounds for crop cultivation have often been eaten up by cattle. The herders and their herds in their search for water and grazing field have often destroyed farmlands, thus bringing them in conflict with local farmers. Farmer herder conflicts have been a recurring incident in the middle belt region and parts of southern Nigeria. The studies of Adishi

and Oluka (2018) indicate that land related violence account for about 31.1% of communal conflicts in Nigeria from 1991 to 2005. This finding is similar to that of many other studies.

This makes the region an area of focus regional and attention on, in respect to the possible effects of climate change and its potential linkages to migration (United Nations Environment Programme 2011). What is causing a lot of people in the Sahel region to migrate include declining rural agricultural and coastal fishery productivity, shifting patterns of nomadic pastoralism, and migration induced by floods, landslides, and other disasters. But since the late 1960s, the Sahel has endured an extensive and severe drought. Desertification occurs when land surfaces are transformed by human activities, including overgrazing, deforestation, surface land mining, and poor irrigation techniques, during a natural time of drought. How is the climate emergency contributing to instability in the Sahel region? What are the climate challenges in Sahel? The Sahel is highly exposed to climate change, yet impacts vary across different regions. The Sahel will gradually become hotter, with some areas experiencing increased, but erratic rainfall. Extreme weather events, including droughts and floods, are expected to intensify in this context. Temperatures there are rising 1.5 times faster than the global average. As a result, droughts and floods are growing longer and more frequent, undermining food production. About 50 million people in the Sahel depend on livestock rearing for survival. But the land available to pastoralists is shrinking (United Nations Environment Programme, 2011).

Climate change and food security in Nigeria

Rainfall controls agricultural activities in Nigeria. The Sahel and Sudan savannah belts represent an extensive grazing areas with cereals and vegetable cultivation more localized around the Fadamas (Fasona and Omojola, 2005). The Guinea savannah is the major food producing areas in Nigeria. It is in the region that root crops, tuber crops, cereals and vegetables are extensively. Crops such as yam, potatoes, cassava, guinea corn, maize and millet massively in the Guinea savannah and distributed to other parts of the country. The rain forest belt also serves as major area for root and tuber crops production but is an exclusive region for cash crops such as oil palm, raffia palm, cocoa, rubber and cashew. These vegetative regions of Nigeria have been adversely affected in different ways by climates change. The persistent drought in the Sudan and Sahel savannah areas has forced many pastoralists out of the region towards the guinea savannah and rain forest areas. This has resulted to increased pressure on lands in these areas. Fallow grounds for crop cultivation have often been eaten up by cattle. The herders and their herds in their search for water and grazing field have often destroyed farmlands, thus bringing them in conflict with local farmers. Farmer herder conflicts have been a recurring incident in the middle belt region and parts of southern Nigeria. The studies of Adishi and Oluka (2018) indicate that land related violence account for about 31.1% of communal conflicts in Nigeria from 1991 to 2005.

Food security is a condition where people symmetrically have access to basic nutritious food. According to the United Nation's Committee on World Food Security. states that food security situation is where everybody has social, physical and economic access to safe, sufficient and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for a healthy and active life. World Food Summit in 1974, defined food security as the availability and adequate supplies of basic food stuffs to offset fluctuation in production, to sustain a steady expansion of food consumption and prices at all times. According to FAO cited by Ani, Anyika and Mutambara (2021), when everybody both old and young do not have adequate economic, physical and social access to food, then it can be said there is food insecurity. In sub-Saharan African states Nigeria has been identified as one that is vulnerable to climatic change (Ughaelu, 2017). Some researchers such as Ayinde, Muchie and Olatunji, 2011; Ughaelu, 2017 and Ikem, (2018), Nigerian food productivity and human suffering have worsened in the past decade due to

the intermittent environmental disasters. In 2012 Nigeria experienced heavy losses in human lives, livestock, crops and as well as human displacement due to severe flooding that has not been recorded in the country in the past decades (Ogbuchi, 2020). The changes in environmental conditions brought by climate change affect the six vegetative zones of Nigeria differently (Ughaelu, 2017). Studies have shown that desertification, high rainfall and flooding have adverse consequences for food production (Tirado, Clarke, Jaykusc, McQuatters-Gollopd, & Frank, 2010; Wossen, Berger, Haile, & Troost, 2018; Uwazie, 2020).

The reason for food security crises currently facing Nigeria is the persistent fall of rainfall gradient in northern parts of Nigeria (Wossen, Berger, Haile, & Troost, 2018). Also, Nigeria has witnessed crop damages, loss of soil fertility, soil toxicity and disruption of soil ecosystem due to persistent flooding of coastlines and southern most part of Nigeria (Wossen, Berger, Haile, & Troost, 2018). The Food and Agricultural organization and World Bank have warned that serious danger is pose to sustainable food production in Nigeria due to climate change (World Bank, 2016; FAO, 2017). Climate change has adverse effect on agricultural productivity in Nigeria leading to lowered productive outputs, with short fall and disruptions in food, and hike in prices of food. The era of food insecurity is becoming intensified across Nigeria as a result of climatic factors which have limited agricultural productivity. Droughts, heavy precipitation, flooding of farmlands; rising temperature, increasing aridity and soil acidity, changes in relative humidity, increase evaporation, among others are induced by climate change with adverse effect on agricultural productivity and food systems in Nigeria (Ani, Anyika, & Mutambara, 2021). Similarly, the livelihood of some 15 million pastoralists in northern Nigeria are threatened by decreasing access to water and pasture shortages linked to climate change (Onuoha & Ezirim, 2010).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study employs adaptation and frustration-aggression theories as its theoretical orientation. According to King (2018), adaptation is a situation of adjusting to expected or actual climate and its effects to avoid harm or exploit beneficial opportunities resulting in migration. Charles Darwin and Alfred Russell Wallace whose studies in the 1830s in the Galapagos Islands established a fixed relationship between organism and its habitat. They believed that the evolution of organisms was connected in some way with adaptation of organisms to changing environmental conditions (King, 2018). Changes in weather patterns and increasing extreme events due to climate change often affect farmers, especially in areas reliant on rain for water in their subsistence agriculture (FAO, 2019; Portal, Xie, Challinor, Cochrane, Howden, Iqbal, Lobell, Travasso, 2014). Under climate change, farmers and pastoralists in Sahel region largely experience increasing variability of both rainfall and temperature which are detrimental to crop plant growth to accelerate poverty. With this conditions, therefore, a range of risk reduction strategies, is employed by households including migration (Jaeger, Dohmen, Falk, Huffman, Sunde, & Bonin, 2010). Migration is often considered as a form of climate change adaptation by which individuals, households, and communities seek to reduce the risks associated with climate change. So migration becomes an effective adaptation strategy for people in climate-vulnerable settings, who lack other options. The migration of cattle herders across Nigeria has no doubt caused frustrations among farmers and herdsmen in many rural communities leading to deadly aggressions. It is argued that the violent conflicts resulting from climate change militate against food security and agribusiness development to generate poverty in Nigeria (Vinke, Rottmann, Gornott, Zabre, Nayna, Schwerdtle, & Sauerborn, 2021).

Frustration-Aggression Theory formulated by (Dollard, Doob, Miller, Mowrer & Sears 1939, cited in Sturme, 2017), presupposes that the existence of frustration always leads to some form of aggression. The consequences of frustration includes among the migrated cattle herders and farmers has resulted in mass killings and destruction of property with attendant poverty in Kaduna, Kogi, Zamfara, Benue, Nasarawa, Bornu, Sokoto villages including villages in south west, south south and south east. The grazing of farmers farmlands and crops by herders' cattle with impunity elicit reactions and frustration from farmers leading to the killings of herd of cattle belonging to the herders. Reaction as reprisal from cattle herders, has always been disastrous by ventilating aggression not only to the farmers but also to individuals not responsible for the cause of their frustration, by killing, sacking people from their homes and burning down villages. Instance s of this abound in the invasions of a Catholic church in Ayar Mbalom village in Benue state by suspected herdsman killing two priests and seventeen parishioners during morning mass on April 24, 2018. After the incident, 16 more villagers were killed in Ali Agundu and Tsav Council wards of Guma Local Government Area (Linda Ikeji, 2018). There is also a case of another massacre of over a hundred persons in Barakin-Ladi and Ri (Nnanwube, 2021).

METHODOLOGY

The study utilizes secondary methods of data gathering. This means using related ideas already presented by other researchers to enhance the study. The secondary sources of data used in the study were basically from textbooks, journals, news papers, the internet, among others. Finally historical analysis was employed for the analysis of the objectives of the paper

ANALYSIS

The effects of climate change on farming activities in Sahel region

The Sahel has been characterized by irregular rainfalls with strong climatic variations which increasingly posed impediment to food security and accelerates poverty in the region. Climate changes have obvious and dire consequences for food supply and poverty, and its phenomenon is a wider threat to the world's productive capacity. Climate change and poverty are deeply mutually inclusive because climate change affects poor people in low-income countries around the world. The poor is further made vulnerable or unable to cope with, adverse effects of climate change including climate variability and extremes, and thereby exacerbates existing inequalities and poverty through its effects on the economy, health, and human rights (Rayner & Malone, 2001). The phenomenon of climate change is about persistent, irreversible land degradation. It is a phenomenon that is more long-term than droughts, with a progressive land degradation. The Sahel countries are affected by desertification with degraded land that can rarely be reclaimed for agriculture. Also the effect of drought and floods, are equally devastating because they result in land degradation and lose of fertility with insufficient rainfall leading to the withering of crops for lack of water to keep the crops with constant flow of water and deaths of livestock for lack of drinking water. So the food security implications are obvious, resulting in the progressive loss of fertile land, that have made the local Sahel population increasingly difficult to sustain subsistence agricultural practices. This is because of the vicious cycles of desertification, droughts, and floods, leading to crop.

Degraded land also destroys natural habitats with human food security effects. For example, desertification in the Sahel has caused loss of biodiversity, including animals around the Sahara Desert. The extinction of animals and birds both in the arid and non-arid zones, has undermined

hunting and food security. The once vast freshwater Lake Chad, spanning the borders of Chad, Cameroon, Niger and Nigeria, stands as a stark illustration of desertification, having shrunk by 90% from over 25,000 square kilometres in the 1960s to just 2,500 square kilometres today (Hough, Malik, Moran, & Pilbeam, 2015). The flow rates of the lake's has two principal feeding rivers, the Chari and Logone, have fallen progressively over recent decades due to drought, a gradual overall decrease in rainfall and increased water demand. The region has suffered the consequences of declining fish stocks in the lake and the erosion of surrounding farmlands (Hough, Malik, Moran, & Pilbeam, 2015). The ecological factors in Sahel region include, climate change and the none availability of natural resources have caused majority of the population in the four countries, to migrate in search of more favourable ecological conditions in other countries . For instance, a lot of migrants have illegally migrated as a result of climate change (such as extreme weather events); crop failure, and scarcity of food to Nigeria with abundance natural resources and minerals. These favourable climatic conditions, constitute one of the major reasons for immigration into Nigeria as many multinational companies that are interested in the abundant mineral resources in the country come to establish in the parts of the country where the mineral resources they need, are located (Ihuoma, 2021).

The impacts of climate change in the Sahel region, have negatively affected individuals' rights to life, health, housing, food, water and sanitation. The majority of people's livelihoods in the Sahel region rely on agriculture, pastoralism or fishing, and these livelihoods are deeply affected by climate change. Apart from agriculture human resource needed for the cultivation of crops is affected by climate change with significant impacts on the rights to life and health. Rising sea levels in coastal areas also results in an increase risk of mortality, injuries, physical ill-health, and mental health conditions. Flooding and heavy rainfall may heighten vulnerability to water or insect-borne diseases, while dry seasons and drought can increase the potential for people to consume unsafe water (United Nations 2021). So it is clear that Sahel region faces many challenges as climate change threatens add to land degradation, destroy vegetation, shrink water resources and food systems, loss of biodiversity and arable land losses through increased incidences of desertification, drought and floods.

Migration of cattle herders as a threat to food security

Climate change constitutes a major threat to food security and result in poverty in Nigeria. The phenomenon through its various manifestations evolve violent conflicts thereby disrupting public safety, to undermined food security and investment. As safety is elusive, there is individual and collective reduction in access to available important natural resources resulting in unprecedented poverty. The inability to access natural resources ultimately hampers the capacity of individual to act in ways that could promote food security and enhance productivity. Population displacement is often rampant due to drastic drop in agricultural output cause by flood, drought and desertification thereby accelerate poverty and want. According to Odo (2012), climate events have undoubtedly led to violent conflicts and insurgency in parts of Nigeria. For instance, Vanguard (2023), reported on 9th April 400 die in 3 weeks following intense killings by suspected herders in Benue state. This is a clear indication that there is strong nexus between climate change and farmer-herder conflicts in various parts of Nigeria. This specific example is not an isolated case in Nigeria as it applies to other African countries. With this killings human resource needed for agricultural production are depleted and those alive are living in perpetual fear of being attacked and poverty. Crops and other agricultural activities in Sahel region are rain-watered, making the countries particularly sensitive to climate change vulnerable. For instance, according to a 2013 World Bank report on Nigeria, the impacts of climate change in Nigeria were discovered to have a declined productivity of livestock and a long-term reduction in crop yields from 20–30 percent, with unpleasant effects on livelihoods, worsening prospects for food

security and generate poverty (Cervigni, Valentini, & Santini 2013). Climate change is challenging Nigeria's goal of food security and a competitive agricultural sector, particularly states in semi-arid areas like the Adamawa state and others are particularly vulnerable to climate change and further pauperizing the vulnerable farmers. The state has experienced inadequate rainfall, serious droughts, and floods have brought low agricultural yields and negatively impacted the state's agricultural productive capacity. Rigaud, Sherbinin, Jones, Abu-Ata, and Adamo (2021), opined that the impact of climate change and its effects on people's livelihoods is being experienced in the Sahelian region. Adding that the climate change has caused the scarcity of natural resources leading to migration and conflict between the nomadic and farmers resulting in poverty and mutual suspicion among them and the nation in general. See figure (1) below showing the migration of cattle as evidence of the real situation.

Figure (1) below,

Photo: Adopted from Davis,2022

Migration largely becomes an option due to the amount of land available for grazing keeps shrinking and the disruptions of livestock migration routes by farms. Also in the course of cattle grazing the land a lots of them go into farmers' farm to graze and damage crops resulting to conflict and poverty. Many pastoralists see the farms as encroaching on their traditional tribal land. This claim and counter-claim often generated violent conflicts between farmers and herders. With death toll of more than 15, 000 since 2010 in West and Central Africa, more than half of which have occurred since 2018. Olobatoke and Amusian (2017), found that both the farmers and herders lose their houses to attacks and reprisals resulting from the encroachments. Farmers constantly live in fear of being attacked by killer herdsmen making their farming environment insecure. (Nweze 2005 in Ofuoku and Isife, 2009), also observed that there are many casualties among farmers as conflicts keep recording in many states including Benue, Plateau, Jigawa, Nasarawa, Kebbi, Imo, Borno, Oyo, and Zamfara. Nasarawa state recorded the highest number of deaths at 47 casualties in a conflict which was sustained for two days. Many farmers across Nigeria have experienced colossal loss of agricultural investments worth huge amounts to the burning of their plantations by herdsmen, harvesting of mature plants to feed cattle, and the routine grazing of cattle on foliage causing unmitigated poverty. In some instances, certain

agribusiness entrepreneurs have experienced this menace for about ten years. The Cable (2017), reports the destruction and burning of 20 hectares of cassava plantations and orange worth 200 billion naira, belonging to a former top government official in Kwara state. Olobatoke and Amusian (2017), found that farmers and herders alike lose their crops and cattle to attacks and reprisals resulting from the encroachments. In their study of Kogi state, about 69.60% of farmers abandoned their farmlands partly due to low productivity. This is supported by Nweze (2005 in Ofuoku & Isife, 2009), who also observed that many herders have lost their herds which has also led to dwindling productivity in their herds. Olanipeku (2018), also reported a similar incidence on a farmland belonging to another former top government official who disclosed that herders burnt his farm as a yearly routine to enable fresh grasses spring up in days for their cattle to graze on. From these incidences crops damaged include: oil palm, yam, and cassava plantations in Ondo state. In another incidence, herdsman set ablaze 100 acres of mangoes and pineapples in Osun state, and about 200 plants of tomato and cucumber in Ikoyi town.

The incidences can also reduce the labour availability for agribusiness owners, and also lead to high production cost in value added goods occasioned by scarcity of primary goods. Such can also rob young agribusiness entrepreneurs of their life savings and investments in one night of conflict from unregulated grazing and bush burning, to the effect of aggravating unemployment and poverty (Nnanwube, 2021). In 2011, deaths toll rose to 116 spread across Abuja, Cross River, Plateau, Benue, Imo, Nasarawa, Katsina, and Zamfara. In same year, Benue attacks which recorded 27 deaths in February and 38 deaths in June being the highest for the year, displaced people with an alleged engagement of herders from Lake Chad (Nnanwube, 2021). It has been observed that the loss of products in storage and reduction in the output and income of farmers negatively affect their savings, credit repayment ability, as well as the economic welfare of urban dwellers who depend on rural farmers for food supply and consequently discouraging farming and rural economic development. This is most glaring in instances of farmers abandoning their farms for fear of insecurity (Nnanwube, 2021).

In Sahel, climate change is making life far more difficult for many pastoralists. The animals need water, but droughts and poor water management have dried up springs and streams, driving herders south, into areas where farming is prevalent. Rainy seasons are becoming more variable, and there have been some devastating droughts. One of the worst, in 2010, killed more than 4.8 million head of cattle in Niger, about a quarter of the country's herd, at an economic cost of more than \$700 million (Davis, 2022). Forced migration due to climate change is directly affecting the peace and security of every Sahel country with increased clashes between nomadic herders and farmers over land use and ownership, resulting in food insecurity (United Nations, 2021). From Chad to Mauritania, the amount of droughts and floods has serious effects on the populations who largely depended on agriculture and livestock for their livelihoods. Furthermore, the scarcity of water resources threatens livelihoods, droughts are more intense, temperatures rising faster than in the rest of the world, climate change causing heavy rains, land drying to absorb the rising waters, destructive river floods and numerous flooding, results in food shortages and widespread poverty (Mayans, 2020).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Focusing on the Sahel in Africa – a region covering Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Chad, Guinea, Mali, Mauritania, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal and the Gambia, with agriculture as the main source of livelihood of the majority of the people living in the area. Increases in temperature or modifications in rainfall quantities and distribution substantially impact on the natural resource on which agriculture depends. The vulnerability of their livelihoods based on agriculture and migration of herders exacerbate poverty, environmental degradation and violent conflict with great impact on food security. It is recommended that a comprehensive programs on water management and irrigation, desertification control, development of alternative sources of energy and the promotion of sustainable agricultural practices by farmers should be the priority concerns of the various governments in the Sahel region. Individuals, families, and communities should not use migration as a strategy for adapting to changing environmental conditions to avoid violent conflict. Migration should be made a choice to the people by the government by investing adequate resources to mitigate a rapidly heating climate. Local communities, including migrants, should be at the centre of building solutions instead of fermenting trouble over ownership of resources. States, including those in the Sahel, as well as regional stakeholders and the international community, should take action on the current and future impacts of climate change causing food insecurity and poverty. It is clear that when food security is affected by climate change, states have an obligation to act and prevent food shortage. Therefore, government should deploy the policies, resources and technologies they need to mitigate and adapt to food and water crises by paying urgent attention to the provision of adequate welfare services including access to drinking water, to help the greatest number of poor populations facing scarcity of resources, to promote water for people, water for agriculture and water for livestock, to support local authorities and the community for better water management and governance in the Sahel. The use of biofuel should be encouraged to reduce the use of fossil fuels and the Nigeria Immigration Service should ensure border tight environment to discourage illegal influx of herders to Nigeria, to reduce violent conflict over resources.

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